

Invited Tutorial Paper on:
**MODELING POWER SEMICONDUCTOR DEVICES
FOR REALISTIC SIMULATION**

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Outline

- Overview
- Physics-based model development
- Simulator implementation
- Model parameter extraction
- Electro-thermal modeling

I. OVERVIEW

- Power electronics is an expanding industry:
 - applications: power conversion, power conditioning, motion control
 - power semiconductors: efficient drive, fast switching, high current
 - technologies developing to integrate power devices and logic circuits.
- Power semiconductor models needed in circuit simulators for CAD:
 - physics-based models for power semiconductors
 - models implemented into circuit simulators
 - extraction sequences to determine model parameters
 - characterization procedures to verify model quality.

NIST IGBT Modeling (1984 – 1994)

- Generic name “IGBT” came from NIST model
- Conventional models not adequate for IGBT:
 - bipolar: ambipolar transport, non-quasi-static
 - MOSFET: nonlinear gate capacitance (D. Schroder)
- Initially NIST IGBT model for device design (1986)
- Evolved to circuit simulation with IGBT availability

Future Direction for Power Device Modeling

- AHDL used extensively for model development
 - multidisciplinary: thermal, mechanical, magnetic
 - reliability aspects included in models
 - circuit board and interconnect
- Preimplemented power topologies
- Virtual prototyping for power system integration

NIST Working Group on Model Validation

- **Objective:** To develop well-defined procedures for comprehensive evaluation of circuit simulator models
- Primary tasks of working group to determine:
 - circuit conditions applicable for device
 - unique characteristics for device type
 - develop test procedure for each

II. PHYSICS-BASED MODEL DEVELOPMENT

- Requirements for circuit simulator model development:
 - compact models to provide efficient simulation times
 - valid for full range of application conditions.
- Techniques used to developed new models:
 - divide structure into regions that can be modeled separately
 - identify device phenomena that occur in each region
 - derive models based upon verifiable approximations.
- May use finite difference simulators for insights, however:
 - models must be valid for general operating conditions
 - not simply mimic particular simulations
 - tabular model generation invalid for nonquasi-static behavior.
- Structures for power semiconductor devices:
 - thick low-doped region to support high breakdown voltages
 - results in low gain bipolar transistors
 - requires low-doped drain MOSFETS.
- Physics for power semiconductor devices:
 - impact ionization and avalanche multiplication
 - high-level injection and ambipolar transport
 - nonquasi-static effects: moving boundary, transport coupling.

EXAMPLE REGIONAL ANALYSIS OF IGBT

- Behaves as bipolar transistor supplied base current by MOSFET.
- IGBT bipolar transistor:
 - low gain, high-level injection
 - base contact at the collector
 - moving base width boundary condition.
- VDMOSFET characteristics:
 - diffused channel dopant density
 - low-doped drain beneath the gate drain overlap.

BASIC SEMICONDUCTOR DEVICE EQUATIONS

$$\nabla^2 \psi = \frac{q}{\epsilon} (N_A - N_D + n - p)$$

$$J_p = -qD_p \nabla p - q\mu_p p \nabla \psi$$

$$J_n = qD_n \nabla n - q\mu_n n \nabla \psi$$

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = -\frac{1}{q} \nabla \cdot J_p + G - U$$

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = \frac{1}{q} \nabla \cdot J_n + G - U$$

QUASI-FERMI POTENTIALS

$$J_p = -q\mu_p p \nabla \phi_p \quad \text{where} \quad p \equiv n_i \exp \left[\frac{q}{kT} (\phi_p - \psi) \right]$$

$$J_n = -q\mu_n n \nabla \phi_n \quad \text{where} \quad n \equiv n_i \exp \left[\frac{q}{kT} (\psi - \phi_n) \right]$$

$$J_T \neq -q(\mu_n n + \mu_p p) \nabla \psi \quad \text{for high-level injection.}$$

DEVELOPMENT OF COMPACT MODELS

- Depletion approximation:
 - separate quasi-neutral regions from space charge regions
 - quasi-neutral regions: $\delta n \approx \delta p$
 - space charge regions: $n = J_n / qv_{nsat}$, $p = J_p / qv_{psat}$.
- Boundary conditions:
 - edge of depletion region: $\delta n = \delta p \approx 0$
 - quasi-equilibrium in forward-biased junctions: $n \cdot p = \text{const.}$
 - equilibrium and charge neutrality at ohmic contacts.
- Ambipolar Transport:
 - low gain: $I_n \sim I_p$
 - high-level injection: $\delta n \approx \delta p \gg |N_D - N_A|$
 - base contact at collector: $I_n(x) + I_p(x) = I_T$.
- Total excess carrier charge conservation:
 - integrate continuity equations across region
 - carriers supplied by currents into boundaries
 - carriers depleted by recombination throughout region
 - can partition charge conservation in neutral region.
- Relate currents to total charge and boundary conditions.
- Must use quasi-fermi potentials for high-level injection.

ANALYSIS OF CONDUCTIVITY-MODULATED DEVICES

AMBIPOLAR TRANSPORT

$$I_p = \frac{1}{1+b} I_T - qAD \frac{\partial p}{\partial x}$$

$$\frac{\partial \delta p}{\partial t} = -\frac{\delta p}{\tau_{HL}} - \frac{1}{qA} \frac{\partial I_p}{\partial x}$$

$$D \frac{\partial^2 \delta p}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\delta p}{\tau_{HL}} + \frac{\partial \delta p}{\partial t}$$

CHARGE CONTROL APPROACH

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = I_n(W) - I_n(0) - \frac{Q}{\tau_{HL}}$$

NON-QUASI-STATIC

$$\frac{\partial \delta p}{\partial t} \not\approx 0$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \delta p(x, t) \not\approx F_{SS}(Q(t)) \\ I_p(W, t) \not\approx G_{SS}(Q(t)) \end{array} \right\} \begin{array}{l} \left| \frac{dQ}{dt} \right| \not\approx \frac{Q}{\tau_b} \\ \left| \frac{dW}{dt} \right| \not\approx \frac{W}{\tau_b} \\ |I_n| \not\approx |I_p| \end{array}$$

NONQUASI-STATIC TRANSIENT MODELING

- Quasi-static transient models use:
 - steady-state shape of the excess carrier distribution
 - steady-state relationship between collector current and charge
- The quasi-static approximation is not valid for IGBT because:
 - electron and hole transport coupled
 - base width changes faster than the base transient speed.
- Static and capacitance characteristics not sufficient to model.

IGBT BIPOLAR TRANSISTOR MODEL

- Nonquasi-static collector current:

$$\delta p'(x) = P'_0 \left[1 - \frac{x}{W'} \right] - \frac{P'_0}{W'D} \left[\frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{W'x}{6} - \frac{x^3}{3W'} \right] \cdot \frac{dW'}{dt}$$

$$I_p(W) = \left(\frac{1}{1+b} \right) I_T + \left(\frac{b}{1+b} \right) \frac{4D_p}{W^2} Q + \frac{C_{bcj}}{3} \cdot \frac{Q}{Q_B} \cdot \frac{dV_{bc}}{dt}$$

- Base charge conservation:

$$I_n(W) = I_{mos} + (C_{dsj} + C_{gd}) \frac{dV_{ds}}{dt} - C_{gd} \frac{dV_{gs}}{dt}$$

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = I_n(W) - \frac{Q}{\tau_{HL}} - \frac{Q^2}{Q_B^2} \cdot \frac{4N_B^2}{n_i^2} I_{sne}$$

- Conductivity modulation:

$$V_{eb} = (\phi_{pej} - \phi_{nej}) + (\phi_{nej} - \phi_{nb})$$

$$(\phi_{nej} - \phi_{nb}) = \int_0^W \frac{J_n(x)}{q\mu_n n(x)} dx$$

$$n(x) = N_B + \delta p(x)$$

VDMOSFET Channel Current

- Different linear and saturation transconductance
 - due to graded channel dopant density
 - evident in low voltage VDMOSFETs and IGBTs

$$I_{mos} = \begin{cases} \frac{K_{Plin} \left[(V_{gs} - V_T)V_{ds} - \frac{K_{Plin}}{K_{Psat}} \frac{V_{ds}^2}{2} \right]}{[1 + \theta(V_{gs} - V_T)]} & \text{for } V_{ds} \leq (V_{gs} - V_T) \frac{K_{Plin}}{K_{Psat}} \\ \frac{K_{Psat}}{2} \frac{(V_{gs} - V_T)^2}{[1 + \theta(V_{gs} - V_T)]} & \text{for } V_{ds} > (V_{gs} - V_T) \frac{K_{Plin}}{K_{Psat}} \end{cases}$$

VDMOSFET Gate-Drain Capacitance

- Two-phase nonlinear gate-drain overlap capacitance
 - low voltage: gate-drain overlap oxide capacitance
 - high voltage: silicon depleted beneath overlap

$$C_{gd} = \begin{cases} C_{oxd} & \text{for } V_{ds} \leq V_{gs} - V_{Td} \\ C_{oxd}C_{gdj}/(C_{oxd} + C_{gdj}) & \text{for } V_{ds} > V_{gs} - V_{Td} \end{cases}$$

$$C_{gdj} = \frac{A_{gd}\epsilon_{si}}{\sqrt{2\epsilon_{si}(V_{dg} + V_{Td})/qN_B}}$$

III. Simulator Implementation

- New models implemented as:
 - macro (subcircuit) models using intrinsic models
 - mathematical models by implementing equations
- Subcircuit modeling has limitations
 - equations must be similar to intrinsic models
 - nonsystematic implementation
- Capability to implement equations is essential

Equation Modeling Capabilities

- System simulators integrate explicit state equations
- SPICE-based simulators:
 - require partial derivatives
 - may not provide adequate access to source code
- IG-SPICE user-defined controlled sources
- Saber simulator provides MAST modeling language

Availability of NIST IGBT Model

- INSTANT 1990 (NIST Simulator)
- Saber 1991 (Analogy Inc.)
- IG-SPICE 1991 (Virginia Tech.)
- EMTP 1992 (Medit. Inst. Tech.)
- SPICE2g6 1993 (Univ. Florida)
- SmartSPICE, P-SPICE, etc. ?

IGBT Models Supplied with Saber

- Models provided as part of Saber 3.2 product
 - IGBT model (1991)
 - electro-thermal IGBT model
 - chip, package, heatsink thermal models
- Motorola IGBT ignition system module
 - model announced at same time as hardware
 - model available from Motorola and Analogy
- Buffer layer IGBT model under development

Implementing IGBT Model Into Saber

- Device currents and heat expressed in terms of:
 - terminal node voltages
 - internal node voltages
 - explicitly defined system variables
- Explicitly defined system variables account for:
 - non-integrable capacitance formulas
 - implicit emitter-base capacitance
 - bias-dependent physical parameters

Equivalent Analog Circuit of Saber IGBT Model

Skeleton Template of Saber IGBT Model

```
# ----- TEMPLATE HEADER -----
Template IGBT anode, gate, cathode =tau_hl
electrical anode, gate, cathode # node type
number tau_hl =1.0u # default lifetime
{ # ----- TEMPLATE BODY -----
  # local declarations

  parameters { # parameters calculated before simulation }

  values { # function of system variables }

  control { # simulator dependent control statemts }

  equations { # equations for system variables } }
```

Equations Section of Saber IGBT Model

```
equations {
  i(gate -> cathode) += d_by_dt(Qgs)
  i(drain -> gate) += Cgd * dVdgd
  i(drain -> cathode) += Imos + Imult + d_by_dt(Qds)
  i(emitter -> cathode) += Icss + Ccer * dVecdt
  i(emitter -> drain) += Ibss + d_by_dt(Q)
  i(anode -> emitter) += Vae/Rb

  dVdgd : dVdgd= d_by_dt(Vdg)
  dVecdt : dVecdt= d_by_dt(Vec)
  Q : Vebq=Veb

  Nsat : Nsat=Ic/(q*A*vpsat) - Imos/(q*A*vnsat)
  mucinv : mucinv = Pm*log( 1. + alpha2/Pm2./3. )/alpha1

  p(tnode) -= power }
```

IV. Model Parameter Extraction

- Determine model parameters from measurements
- Physics-based models have unknown parameters:
 - different device part numbers and manufacturers
 - statistical process variations
 - inaccuracies in compact model approximations
- Develop libraries of manufacturers' part numbers

Development Of Extraction Procedure

- Integral part of model development
- Sequence determines a few parameters at each step:
 - electrical feature chosen to isolate parameters
 - fit few parameters to simplified model expression
 - values used by subsequent extraction steps
- Multiple parameter optimization used sometimes
- Data book information not sufficient for extraction

IGBT Extraction Sequence

- Dynamic measurements access internal bipolar
- Static measurements for MOSFET parameters
 - bipolar model relates internal MOSFET current to terminal currents
- Gate and gate-drain charge isolate capacitances
- Extractions performed versus temperature

IGBT Model Parameters

A	0.1 cm^2	Chip size
τ_{HL}	$0.3 - 8.0 \mu s$	Tail decay rate
I_{sne}	$6.0 \times 10^{-14} \text{ A}$	Tail size -vs- current
W_B	$93 \mu m$	Tail size -vs- V_A
N_B	$2 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$	Tail size -vs- V_A
V_T	5.0 V	Saturation current -vs- V_{gs}
$K_{P_{sat}}$	0.4 A/V^2	Saturation current -vs- V_{gs}
$K_{P_{lin}}$	0.75 A/V^2	On-state voltage -vs- V_{gs}
C_{gs}	0.6 nF	Gate charge
C_{oxd}	1.6 nF	Gate charge
A_{gd}	0.05 cm^2	Gate-drain charge

Dynamic Measurements Characterize Bipolar

Dynamic Waveform Analysis Test System

Tail Decay Rate for Constant Voltage

- Base lifetime extracted from tail decay rate
- Model equations simplified for
 - constant anode voltage or clamp voltage
 - zero MOSFET channel current after gate switched

$$\frac{d \ln I_T}{dt} = \frac{dI_T}{dt} / I_T = -\frac{1}{\tau_{HL}} \left(1 + \frac{I_T}{I_k^\tau} \right)$$

Extrapolated Value of Base Lifetime

Tail Size Versus Voltage and Current

$$\beta_{tr,V} \equiv \frac{I_T(0^+)}{I_T(0^-) - I_T(0^+)} = \beta_{tr,V}^{max} \left(1 + \frac{I_T(0^+)}{I_k} \right)^{-1}$$

- Use lifetime from previous extraction step
- Tail size versus current gives: $I_{sne} = f(I_k, W, \tau_{HL})$:
- Zero-current intercept gives: $\beta_{tr,V}^{max} = f(W, \tau_{HL})$
- $W = W_B - \sqrt{2\epsilon_{si}/qN_B} \cdot \sqrt{V_A}$ gives: N_B, W_B

Tail Size Versus Current and Extrapolation

Static Measurements Characterize MOSFET

High Power Pulsed Steady-State Measurements

Saturation Current Versus Gate Voltage

- Threshold and transconductance obtained by:
 - divide external saturation current by bipolar gain
 - bipolar gain known from previous extraction steps
 - square-root saturation current vs. gate voltage

$$I_{mos}^{sat} = I_T^{sat} / (1 + \beta_{ss})$$

$$\beta_{ss} = f(\tau_{HL}, W_B, N_B, I_{sne}, I_T)$$

$$\sqrt{I_{mos}^{sat}} = \sqrt{K_{psat}/2} \cdot (V_{gs} - V_T)$$

Extrapolated MOSFET Saturation Current

On-State Voltage Versus Gate Voltage

- Series resistance and linear region transconductance:
 - constant I_T and low V_A simplify expression
 - on-state voltage versus $1/(V_{gs} - V_T)$
 - all other parameters known from previous steps

$$V_A = V_r + \frac{I_T}{(1 + \beta_{ss})K_{Plin}} \left(\frac{1}{V_{gs} - V_T} \right)$$

$$V_r \equiv V_{eb} + R_s \cdot I_T + \frac{I_T \theta}{(1 + \beta_{ss})K_{Plin}}$$

Extrapolated On-state Voltage Versus $1/(V_{gs} - V_T)$

V. Electro-Thermal Network Simulation

- Traditional SPICE-based simulators:
 - temperature is chosen by user
 - temperature remains constant during simulation
- New electro-thermal simulation methodology:
 - dissipated power supplies heat to thermal network
 - simulator determines temperature distribution
 - IGBT model uses instantaneous temperature

Schematic Entry of Electro-Thermal Network

Electro–Thermal Semiconductor Models

- Dynamic electro-thermal semiconductor models:
 - physics-based semiconductor models
 - temperature-dependent model parameters
 - temperature-dependent properties of silicon
- Electro-thermal models describe:
 - components of currents between electrical nodes
 - dissipated power flow into the thermal nodes

Temperature–Dependent IGBT Model Parameters

$$\tau_{HL}(T_j) = \tau_{HL0} \cdot (T_j/T_0)^{\tau_{HL1}}$$

$$I_{sne}(T_j) = \frac{I_{sne0} \cdot (T_j/T_0)^{I_{sne1}}}{\exp [14000 \cdot (1/T_j - 1/T_0)]}$$

$$V_T(T_j) = V_{T0} + V_{T1} \cdot (T_j - T_0)$$

$$K_p(T_j) = K_{p0} \cdot (T_0/T_j)^{K_{p1}}$$

Temperature Variation of IGBT Base Lifetime

Temperature Variation of IGBT Threshold Voltage

Thermal Network Component Models

- Thermal network described by:
 - interconnection of thermal network components
 - topology specified similarly to electrical network
- Component models from discretized heat equation:
 - grid increases logarithmically from heat source
 - various 3-dimensional symmetry conditions
 - nonlinear thermal conductivity and convection
- Defined by structural and material parameters

Discretization of Heat Diffusion Equation

- Heat Equation (partial differential equation):

$$\nabla \cdot (k(T)\nabla T) = \rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t}$$

- Discretized heat equation (ordinary differential eq.):

$$\frac{T_{i+1} - T_i}{R_{i,i+1}} - \frac{T_i - T_{i-1}}{R_{i-1,i}} = \frac{dH_i}{dt}$$

$$H_i = C_i \cdot T_i$$

On-State Voltage Versus Temperature

Saturation Current Versus Temperature

Electro-Thermal Simulation of Short Circuit

Thermal Response of Chip and Package

Electro-Thermal Simulation of System Warm-up

Electro-Thermal Simulation of PWM Inverter

Load Current for Frequency of 20 kHz

Chip, Package, and Heatsink Temperature

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